

IMPACT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLES ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG EMPLOYEES IN LIBYAN PUBLIC BANKS

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to explore the relationship between Transformation leadership styles (namely, Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individualized consideration) and organizational commitment among the employees working for public banks in Libya. In this study quantitative research method was followed as a research methodology. The researcher distributed a total of 411 questionnaires on the employees of these banks, on which they were all returned and fully answered and valid for analysis. The researcher will use SPSS and Smart PLS as means of data analysis. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, and Intellectual Stimulation with organizational commitment. However, the relationship between Individualized consideration and organizational commitment was statistically insignificant.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Employee, Organizational Commitment, Efficiency, Business Success

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector in Libya is the backbone of the economic structure, which drives development growth of the economy (Al-mari et al., 2007). Due it is providing funds and financial services to the business sector and contributing to economic growth (Cohen et al., 2007). During the last decade, commercial banks in Libya witnessed important developments, which were reflected in the development of most of the basic items in their financial positions, as a result of the monetary and banking policy pursued by the Central Bank of Libya on the one hand, and the efforts made by banks in order to raise the level of their performance and improve the level of their services on the other hand (Libyan Central Bank, 2018).

The banking sector in Libya is regulated by the government. The Libyan Central Bank monitors all banks, and issues procedures and instructions that regulate the work of banks (Allen et al., 2011; Shuaieb, 2013). The central bank is managed by a board of directors consisting of a governor, deputy governor, and six other members (Woldie, & Dofan, 2007) who usually represent other financial and economic interests (Shoaib, 2013). The Governor is the Bank's CEO and is also responsible for setting and implementing plans and policy for the bank, managing all of its affairs, and representing the bank in all its internal and external relationships with all parties (Allen et al., 2011; Shuaieb, 2013; Woldie & Dofan, 2007).

Libyan public banks don't provide the appropriate organizational environment that could encouraged their employee to be commitment to the banks. In this regard, Altaboli (2017),

Alajili, and Noor (2018), and Salem (2019) mentioned that the work environment in Libyan public banks is unsatisfactory and uninspiring which led to the low of employees' organizational commitment. And low of organizational commitment will led to low of employee's performance to deliver desirable service quality (Al-Refaei et al, 2019) In this regard, when employees uncommitted to the banks they will not perform a good service to their customer (Al-Refaei et al, 2019) because when employee uncommitted to the bank they will be unwilling to exert any additional effort to benefit their organization (Al-Refaei et al, 2019).

Previous studies conformed relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment such as (Chai et al., 2017; Jain et al., 2019; Keskes et al., 2018; Novianti, 2021; Vipraprastha et al., 2018). Previous studies don't clarify how transformational leadership effect organizational commitment, under which mechanism transformational leadership effect organizational commitment, don't clarify the mechanism make understanding this relationship unclear (Eliyana & Ma'arif, 2019; Purwanto, 2020). Scholar suggested that, transformational leadership effect organizational commitment by social exchange mechanism (Eliyana & Ma'arif, 2019; Purwanto, 2020). Therefore, current study come to full this gap, by examine the effect of transformational leadership on organizational commitment under social exchange theory in banks sector in Libya.

Overall, the aim of this study is to assess the relationship between transformational leadership 4Is, namely; Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individualized consideration, on the Organizational Commitment among the public banks in Libya. In this study, the quantitative research methods will be used to achieve this aim on a sample of employees working for the aforementioned banks.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Transformational Leadership

In the 1970s, Burns introduced a new model of leadership style in which the leader goes beyond satisfaction to the basic needs of the subordinate, in terms of Maslow's (1954) hierarchy of needs, by inspiring and empowering the subordinate to a higher level of motivation. Based on this theory people are motivated by five levels of needs: physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization (Turnnidge, 2018). The hierarchy of needs theory is a content-based theory that focuses on understanding and identifying peoples' needs (Kwan, 2020). The new leadership style is known as the transformational leadership style. This type of leadership focuses on identifying leadership behaviors that influence the values and aspirations of subordinates, activate the subordinates' higher-order needs, and arouse them to transcend their self-interest for the sake of their organization (Fourie, 2019). Bass in the 1980s further developed it. The essence of the theory is the distinction between transformational and transactional leadership. The two types of leadership were defined in terms of the component behaviors used to influence followers the effects of the leader on followers (Kwan, 2020).

Siangchokyoo (2020) developed Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire to assess leadership behaviors in different settings (e.g., military, education, business, industry). Fourie (2019) concluded that assessing leadership approaches illustrated that transformational leadership style and use of the MLQ would be the best instrument to examine the leadership questions posed (Siangchokyoo, 2020). Transformational leadership theory has risen from differences among transformational from transactional behaviors (Kwan, 2020). Transactional leaders focus on rewards and identification for successful duty execution. They provide feedback and monitor and correct subordinates' behaviors (Asmawi, 2021). Although transactional behaviors create a base for successful leadership, they cannot adequately motivate their subordinate to do best their tasks. Bass (1997) stated that transformational leadership theory was developed to augment or increase transactional behavior's effects in predicting human attainment. Due to these reasons and other previously mentioned advantages of transformational behaviors and supervisory committee members' recommendation, this study focused on transformational behaviors of Iranian high school coaches (rather than transactional). Therefore, in this study the researcher selected a total 20 items from 45 MLQ 's items related to the transformational behavior.

Based on the researcher knowledge, there is no transformational leadership questionnaire in an organizational setting. However, according to Smith (2019), the transformational leadership style is helpful for coaches or administrators in sport settings. Many researchers have used the only transformational scale of MLQ in sport settings (Arnold, 2013; Fourie, 2019; López-Zapata, 2017; Martin, 2017; Muppithi, 2021; Rad, 2021; Smith, 2019; Usanov, 2021).

Four scales (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and Individualized consideration) were used to measure transformational leadership behavior (Choi, 2019b). In addition, several researchers examined the transformational leadership style of physical education teachers only using four subscales: idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and individualized consideration (Vele, 2018). In another study, researchers examined students' perceptions of parental transformational leadership using the MLQ developed by Avolio and Bass (1995). Again, they only used four subscales of transformational leadership: idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and individualized consideration.

With transformational leadership, the followers feel trust, administration, loyalty, and respect toward the leader, and they are motivated to do more than they initially expected to do. According to Al-Awamleh (2020)), the leader transforms and motivates followers by (1) making them more aware of the importance of task outputs, (2) inducing them to transcend their self-interest for the sake of the organization or team, and (3) activating their higher-order needs. On the contrary, transactional leadership involves an exchange process that may result in followers' compliance with leader requests but is not likely to generate enthusiasm and commitment to task objectives (Soomro, 2020).

Further, transformational and transactional leadership are distinct but not mutually exclusive processes. Transformational leadership increases followers' motivation and performance more than transactional leadership (Bass, 1994). Transformational leaders' areas top managers who create changes in a significant way. (Alkadash et al., 2020) stated that transformational leaders are high-quality team leaders because they allow employees to cooperate in change and align personal values with organizational values. These leaders improve the quality of relationships and commitment of subordinates (Alkadash et al., 2020). Also, they emphasize innovation, change, and entrepreneurship and often lead their organization based on three acts consisting:

- 1) Transformational leaders identify the need for new life of organization. Therefore, Transformational leaders have to prepare to match with rapid organizational environment changes.
- 2) Transformational leaders make a new idea. They envisage the changed organization and inspire employees to make it become a reality.
- 3) Transformational leaders institutionalize change. They create a structure for change (Ennis, 2018).

Results have revealed that the transformational style can increase the performance of subordinates (Alghusin, 2020). Followers' values and beliefs determine transformational leadership behaviors (Bass, 1994); therefore, based on these values and beliefs, transformational leaders motivate their followers to work hard and show high performance (Crane, 2018). On the other hand, the transformational leadership style improves both performances and maximizes the potential of subordinates (Al-Obthani, 2019). In addition, transformational leaders help their followers to get high levels of satisfaction and develop followers' commitment to the group and organization (Nguyen, 2019). Transformational leaders attempt to raise the quality of followers' requests, improve awareness, and believe in followers' goals and ideals (Al-Obthani, 2019).

Transformational theories (Relationship theories) concentrate upon the connections formed between leaders and followers. A few researchers believe that leaders motivate and inspire people by helping group members see the importance of the task (Alneyadi, 2019; Donkor, 2021; Nguyen, 2019). In other words, transformational leaders do not only focus on the performance of group members, but they also want each person to fulfil their potential. Thus, these leaders often have high ethical and moral standards. On the other hand, the main advantages of transformational leadership styles are to focus on the connections formed between leaders and followers, motivation, inspiration and arousing team spirit of people by helping group members to realize the importance of the value of their task (Alneyadi, 2019; Donkor, 2021; Nguyen, 2019).

Harb (2019) believe that transformational leadership is naturally multidimensional. Therefore, they developed the Transformational Leadership Behavior Inventory to evaluate the subjects'

perception of the transformational leadership behaviors in their respective organizations. This transformational model has six key dimensions consist of:

1. Identifying and articulating a vision- Behavior on the part of the leader aimed at identifying new opportunities for his or her organization, and developing, articulating, and inspiring others with his or her vision of the future.
2. Providing an appropriate model- Behavior on the part of the leader that sets an example for employees to follow consistent with values the leader espouses.
3. Fostering the acceptance of group goals- Behavior on the part of the leader aiming at promoting cooperation among employees and getting them to work together toward a common goal.
4. High performance expectations- Behavior that demonstrates the leader 's expectations for excellence, quality, and/or high performance on the part of followers.
5. Providing individualized support- Behavior on the part of the leader which indicates that he/she respects followers and is concerned about their personal feeling and needs.
6. Intellectual stimulation- Behavior on the part of the leader that challenges followers to re-examine some of their assumptions about their work and rethink how it can be performed (Hincapié-Montoya, 2018).

According to Alghusin (2020); Chan (2019), transformational leadership factors are: (1) Idealized influence (attributed), (2) idealized influence (behavior), (3) Inspirational motivation, (4) Intellectual stimulation and (5) Individualized consideration. Organizations emphasize the idea of leadership in training managers to move a group or the association forward. Inside initiative, the adequacy of the transformational versus value- based pioneer is transactional leader is often debated. Transactional leadership relies on a give and take understanding, whereby subordinates have a feeling of obligation to the leader in return for some reward. Transformational leadership, then again, includes a committed connection between the leader and his followers. Bass (1998) distinguished and expounded on four essential components that underlie transformational leadership.

Transformational leadership theory is built on the four Is. These represent leaders' roles that bring out expected outcomes such as organizational commitment, transformational leadership environment, and satisfaction. These lead to improved institutional performance and love for the Organization. Taping on this theory, in bank organizations, a transformational climate will lead to satisfying staffing with a great desire to grow and commit to the organization's mission. This would lead to less turnover and consequently improved performance (See Figure 1)

Figure 1 : Transformational Leadership theory perspective

As per the theory, the 4Is of transformational leadership bring about trust, commitment, sense of belonging that facilitate learning and satisfaction. The independent variables are Trust, Learning and satisfaction, while Turnover of staff, Client's growth and profitability are the key parameters to measure the performance of Microfinance staff. This study is anchored on the theory of transformational leadership as fronted by Bass (1988). Developed in the 20th Century, transformational leadership theory was first laid as an analysis of political leadership. Before then, a lot of attention was on the study of great leaders and who they were.

Burns (2018) proposed leadership types that occur when a person involves another in a way that uplifts them to higher motivation and morality. The basement of transformational leadership is that it must raise followers from low needs to a higher level of need. This is in line with Maslow (1954) theory of hierarchy of needs. In expanding this theory, Bass (2018) defines a leader as someone who incites others to actualize more than initially contrived. This is achieved by getting awareness to levels that bring the outcomes, their importance, and the means to achieve them. In this respect, followers are tuned to improve beyond self-preservation for a team and firm (Burns, 2018).

Rao (2019) defines transformational leadership as a process where people develop and create organizations that accomplish extraordinary results. Transformational leadership distinguishes itself in that the leader plays the role of rallying others behind their mission and objectives to achieve in a remarkable way (Harb, 2019). Drawing from the above, transformative leaders generate higher-order needs of the employees, making them better. They build relationships guided by mutual trust and push for a well-articulated vision that members unite along. Transformational leaders motivate followers to deliver beyond their expectations and be committed to an organization's objectives (Al-Shibami, 2019). The style used by transformational leaders rubs through followers, influencing their behavior by creating a psychological contract (Mishra, 2020).

2.2 Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment defined as the strength of identification of an individual with his organization and involvement in a particular organization (Porter, Steers, Mowday, and Boulian, 1974; Meyer & Allen, 1997). According to Robbins & Judge, (2018) defined organizational commitment as the degree of employee identify with organization and its goals and wishes to continue as member in this organization.

Organizational commitment defined in current study as the degree of employee indentation with the public banks in Libya they work in, and acceptance the banks goals, and wishes to continue and willing to exert extra efforts to achieve or succeed banks goals (Novianti, 2021).

2.3 Overview of the Research Framework

Transformational leaders inspire team members because they expect the best from each of them and feel responsible for their actions. Also, this type of leader provides information, advice, support and encouragement to workers, increasing their motivation and optimizing their performance. According to Bass and Riggio (2014), the transformational components are:

- Idealized influence or charisma. It is the degree to which the leader behaves admirably, in a way that causes followers to identify themselves with that leader (Bass & Riggio, 2014). Leaders of this type are described as charismatic and are perceived by followers as possessing a high degree of morality, trust, and integrity. They show conviction, emphasize trust, position themselves on difficult issues and emphasize the importance of purpose, commitment and ethical consequences of decisions. These leaders are admired as role models generating pride, loyalty, trust and alliance around a common purpose.
- Inspirational Motivation. It is the degree to which the leader articulates that vision that is attractive and inspiring to the followers and challenges them with high standards, transmits optimism about achieving goals and lends meaning to daily tasks (Judge et al., 2014). These leaders have the ability to motivate their employees to make them rethink how to solve problems, encouraging them to be innovative and creative.
- Intellectual stimulation. It is the degree to which the leader questions assumptions, takes risks, asks for ideas from the followers, and encourages creativity in the followers (Judge et al., 2014). These are leaders who question old assumptions, traditions and beliefs, inspire new perspectives and ways of doing things, and encourage the expression of ideas. If a collaborator is wrong, they will not be punished by making the issue public, but are encouraged to contribute ideas even if these ideas do not agree with those of their responsible.
- Individualized Consideration: The degree to which the leader meets the needs of each follower, acts as their mentor or coach, and listens to their concerns and needs (Judge et al., 2014). They are leaders who consider individual needs, abilities, and aspirations,

promote a two-way communication with their collaborators, not just a mere transmission of information, which is why they are considered as people who listen.

This study applies the Transformational Leadership framework. Overall, this research examines Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individualized consideration to determine Organizational Commitment among the Libyan public banks. As such, Figure 2 displays the proposed framework.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher will utilize quantitative research methods. Primary data was collected from employees working for five public banks that have operating branches in Tripoli, on which the respondents were selected based on non-probability sampling. The researcher distributed a total of 411 questionnaires on the employees of these banks, on which they were all returned and fully answered and valid for analysis. The researcher will use SPSS and Smart PLS as means of data analysis.

4. INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

The development of instruments was carefully executed to reflect the nature of this research. As such, the questionnaire was designed to include 32 items, and the variables were measured using the five-point Likert scale, with five standing for ‘Strongly Agree’ and one standing for ‘Strongly Disagree’. Since the participants spoke Arabic, the survey needed to be accurately translated from English to Arabic. As a result, a reverse translation was conducted, which is a common method for determining the accuracy of a translation in a cross-cultural survey (Brislin, 1970). Furthermore, the validated instruments listed in Table 1 were adopted from relevant prior researches to measure the variables in this research.

Table 1: Research Instrument

Construct	No of Items	Citation
Idealized Influence	4	Bass & Avolio (2000)
Inspirational Motivation	4	Bass & Avolio (2000)
Intellectual Stimulation	4	Bass & Avolio (2000)
Individualized consideration	4	Bass & Avolio (2000)
Organizational Commitment	16	(Allen & Meyer, 1990)

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The current study has assessed the proposed model in two steps consisting of the assessment of the measurement model (outer model) and the assessment of the structural model (inner model). However, before these two steps, a brief explanation is given regarding the respondents' profiles.

5.1 Respondent Profile

The first segment of the instrument compiled information on background profile of the respondents which comprises of their Gender, Age, and Educational Level. The characteristics of each demographic profile are described below in Table 2.

Table 2: Respondent Profile

Item	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	244	59.4
	Female	167	40.6
Age group	20 – 25 years	43	10.5
	26 – 30 years	117	28.5
	31 – 35 years	144	35.0
	36 – 40 years	75	18.2
	41 years and above	32	7.80
Education level	High School	9	2.2
	Diploma	58	14.1
	Bachelor	272	66.2
	Masters	61	14.8
	Doctorate	11	2.7

5.2 Measurement Model

The research model of this study was tested using SmartPLS 3.3. In addition, an examination was conducted regarding the measurement model (validity and reliability of the measures). As a result, not all of the constructs in the first run recorded AVE values higher than 0.5 for each group of data (Hair et al., 2017), as the lowest AVE value reported is for Organizational Commitment (OC) (0.422). Furthermore, OC3, OC4, OC12 and OC13 scored low factor

loadings (-0.029, 0.004, 0.009, and -0.010 respectively) which all were below the recommended level of 0.4 by Ramayah et al. (2018). Therefore, a form of modification was considered in the second run and, consequently, OC3, OC4, OC12 and OC13 were deleted to achieve satisfactory levels of AVE and factor loadings (Ramayah et al., 2018). Overall, all variables have achieved the cut-off point, as illustrated in Table 3 (see the results also in Figure 3).

Table 3: Convergent Validity Results

Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
IC1	0.789	0.755	0.842	0.573
IC2	0.841			
IC3	0.709			
IC4	0.678			
II1	0.751	0.798	0.868	0.623
II2	0.784			
II3	0.808			
II4	0.813			
IM1	0.821	0.802	0.871	0.628
IM2	0.839			
IM3	0.764			
IM4	0.742			
IS1	0.768	0.832	0.888	0.665
IS2	0.845			
IS3	0.789			
IS4	0.855			
OC1	0.710	0.929	0.939	0.563
OC2	0.709			
OC5	0.780			
OC6	0.770			
OC7	0.761			
OC8	0.822			
OC9	0.772			
OC10	0.761			
OC11	0.711			
OC14	0.803			
OC15	0.723			
OC16	0.668			

(*) OC3, OC4, OC12 and OC13 were deleted due to low factor loading and AVE, as OC AVE was 0.422 before deleting OC3 (factor loading -0.029), OC4 (factor loading 0.004), OC12 (factor loading 0.009), and OC13 (factor loading -0.010).

Figure 3: Model of PLS algorithm results (Measurement model)

Secondly, the discriminant validity was examined to assess how truly distinct a construct is from other constructs. In the area of distinguishing validity, the correlations between variables. The estimation of the model did not exceed 0.95, as suggested by Kline (2016) (Kline, 2016), and the validity was tested based on measurements of the square root of the average variance calculated for a construct and the correlations between constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Kline, 2016). Hence, Table 4 contains the results of the Fornell and Larcker Criterion and shows no value above the recommended cutoff point of 0.95 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker Criterion

	IC	II	IM	IS	OC
IC	0.757				
II	0.004	0.789			
IM	0.084	0.655	0.792		
IS	0.159	0.660	0.730	0.815	
OC	0.110	0.662	0.693	0.733	0.750

Moreover, the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) is a calculation that estimates the actual correlation between two constructs if they were properly assessed (i.e., if they were perfectly reliable) (Gold et al., 2001; Hair et al., 2017). Furthermore, HTMT is the average of all correlations of indicators across constructs measuring different constructs

(i.e., HTMT correlations) compared to the (geometric) mean of the average correlations of indicators measuring the same construct (i.e., HTMT correlations) and can be used to assess discriminant validity, on which Gold et al. (2001) recommended the accepted level of HTMT to be below 0.90. As such, the accepted level of HTMT is 0.90 can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: HTMT Criterion

	IC	II	IM	IS	OC
IC					
II	0.052				
IM	0.119	0.810			
IS	0.197	0.793	0.879		
OC	0.137	0.761	0.792	0.824	

5.3 Structural Model

The path model's theoretical or conceptual aspect is represented by the structural model. The structural model, also known as the inner model in PLS-SEM, contains the latent variables and their path relations (Hair et al., 2017). The next step after the evaluation of the measurement model is to assess the structural model. In sync with PLS-SEM, there are five steps required to assess the structural model according to Hair et al. (2017) including the assessment of collinearity (step one), assessment of the path coefficients (step two), coefficient of determination (R^2 value) (step three), blindfolding and predictive relevance Q^2 (step four), and effect size f^2 (step five) (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 6 illustrates the results of PLS bootstrapping consisting of the Beta value, t-values, p-values, hypothesis results (whether supported or not) BCILL, BCIUL, f^2 , and VIF scores. Furthermore, Figure 4 summarizes the results of the structural model and PLS bootstrapping.

Table 6: Summary of Structural Model (PLS bootstrapping)

H		Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	5.00%	95.00%	f^2	VIF	R2	Q2
H1	II -> OC	0.245	0.043	5.631	0	0.161	0.315	0.178	2.032	0.620	0.313
H2	IM -> OC	0.248	0.055	4.468	0	0.153	0.336	0.167	2.416		
H3	IS -> OC	0.387	0.054	7.124	0	0.304	0.481	0.156	2.526		
H4	IC -> OC	0.027	0.035	0.783	0.217	-0.027	0.09	0.002	1.046		

The first step in the structural model is to assess collinearity issues. It is vital to safeguard against collinearity issues between the constructs before performing a latent variable analysis in the structural model. As such, the collinearity has been measured by measuring the VIF value. The threshold value for the assessment is 3.3, following the recommendation of Diamantopoulos and Siguaw (2006) (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2006). In this study, as illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, all inner VIF values for the constructs are within the range of 1.046 to 2.416. All are less than 3.3, thus indicating that collinearity is not a concern in this study.

Figure 4 : Structural Model (PLS bootstrapping)

First: Assessment of the Structural Model for Collinearity Issues

5.3.1 Assessing the Significance of the Structural Model Relationships

The bootstrapping approach was used to provide data for each path relationship in the model to evaluate the hypotheses, as shown in Table 6. In PLS, bootstrapping is a nonparametric test that involves repeated random sampling with replacement from the original sample to generate a boot-strap sample and achieve standard errors for hypothesis testing (Hair et al., 2017). Chin (2010) recommended bootstrapping with 1000 samples when it came to the number of resampling (Chin, 2010). Nine hypotheses for the constructions have been developed in this study. T-statistics for all pathways were computed using the bootstrapping tool in SmartPLS 3.3 to assess the significance level. A significance level of 0.05, a two-tailed test, and 1000 subsamples was used in the bootstrapping. For the two-tailed test, the critical value for the significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) is 1.645 (Ramayah et al., 2018). The value of the path coefficients has a standardized value between -1 and +1, according to the data in Table 6. (Values from 0.14 to 0.485). Estimated route coefficients approaching +1 indicate strong positive associations, according to Hair et al., (2017), and the closer the number comes to zero, the weaker the relationships get. In the next step, toward conducting the T-test, relationships are found to have T-values of more than or equal to 1.645. Therefore, these relationships are significant at 0.05 for H1, H2, and H3. While H4 will be rejected. A summary of these findings is illustrated in Table 6.

5.3.2 The Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The next stage is to evaluate the model's predictive accuracy through the derived value of the coefficient of determination (R^2). The value of R^2 is linked to the model's predictive power and ranges from zero to one, with a higher value indicating a higher level of predictive accuracy (Hair et al., 2017). Using the Smart PLS algorithm, the value of R^2 has been calculated as shown in Table 6. Furthermore, Hair et al. (2017) detailed 3 different levels of R^2 scores. If R^2 is above 0.75 it will be considered as substantial, if R^2 is above 0.50 it will be considered as moderate, and if R^2 is above 0.25 it will be considered as weak, while if R^2 below 0.25 it will be considered as unacceptable. As per Table 7, the scores of R^2 for OC are considered as in Moderate level as recommended by Hair et al. (2017).

Table 7: The coefficient of determination (R^2)

Construct	R^2
OC	0.620

5.3.3 Assessment of the effect size (f^2)

In this stage, the effect sizes (f^2) have been evaluated. The value of f^2 is connected to the relative impact of a predictor construct on endogenous constructs. According to Sullivan and Feinn (2012), aside from reporting the p-value, both the substantive significance (effect size) and statistical significance (p-value) are crucial to be reported (Sullivan & Feinn, 2012). Furthermore, to measure the effect size, a guideline set by Cohen (1988) has been followed (Cohen, 1988). Based on the study of Cohen (1988), the values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effects respectively (Cohen, 1988). As it can be viewed in Table 6, H4 has f^2 values less than .02 which indicated no effect at all, H1, H2, and H3 have f^2 values more than .15 which indicated medium size of effect.

5.3.4 Assessment of the Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Table 8: The Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Construct	Q^2
PER	0.313

As the final step, the predictive relevance of the model has been assessed through the blindfolding procedure, as suggested by Hair et al. (2017) (Hair et al., 2017), Table 8 provides the Q^2 value (along with the R^2 values) of all the endogenous constructs. The Q^2 value was above zero and therefore supported the model's predictive relevance regarding the endogenous latent variables as recommended by Stone (1974), Geisser (1974) and Hair et al. (2017). Finally, there was no issue associated with a single-indicator construct as a predictor construct in this study (Geisser, 1974; Hair et al., 2017; Stone, 1974).

6. DISCUSSION

This study applies the Transformational Leadership framework. Overall, this research examines Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individualized consideration to determine Organizational Commitment among the Libyan public banks. As such, Figure 2 displays the proposed framework.

The relationship between Idealized Influence and Organizational Commitment was statically positive and significant. In the quantitative data analysis, Idealized Influence have 24.4% of predictive power (β) in achieving high level of Organizational Commitment (with p-value below the cut-off point 0.05), which means the Idealized Influence affects the Organizational Commitment. Hence, H6 was supported. Speaking of the current study, Idealized Influence is established to be significantly affecting the Organizational Commitment in Libya. Libyan public banks should consider the behaviours of the leaders that instil pride in followers for being associated with the leader, as these behaviour will encourage high level of Organizational Commitment. This result is in consistent with the previous published literature.

A study was conducted by Afshari (2021) to evaluate the correlations between the idealised influence component of transformational leadership (TL) and employee organisational commitment in two distinct cultural settings. Specifically, the researchers looked at Chinese and American workplaces. These findings demonstrated statistically significant relationships between two forms of idealised influence – attributed and behaviour – and the employees' organisational commitment in the Iranian sample. The attributed form of idealised influence was found to be significantly more prevalent than the behaviour form. On the other hand, in the sample from Australia, idealised influence behaviour was the only one that demonstrated a significant effect on employee commitment. In addition to this, the results demonstrated that recognised motivation acts as a mediator between idealised influence relationship and organisational commitment (Afshari, 2021).

In addition, the research conducted by Al-Quraan (2016) was aimed at determining the impact of transformational leadership (idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration) on organisational commitment (affective, normative, and continuance) at Jordan Ahli Bank branches from the employees' point of view. At Jordan Ahli Bank, the current research has demonstrated that transformational leadership dimensions, such as idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration, have a significant impact on organisational commitment, which can be broken down into three categories: affective, normative, and continuance (Al-Quraan, 2016).

The relationship between Inspirational Motivation and Organizational Commitment was statically positive and significant. In the quantitative data analysis, Inspirational Motivation have 24.1% of predictive power (β) in achieving high level of Organizational Commitment (with p-value below the cut-off point 0.05), which means the Inspirational Motivation affects the Organizational Commitment. Hence, H7 was supported. Speaking of the current study,

Inspirational Motivation is established to be significantly affecting the Organizational Commitment in Libya. The inducement that increases follower's cognitive and behavioural patterns to accept challenging tasks and achieve desirable results among the leaders in the Libyan public banks will encourage the employees to show more Organizational Commitment. This result is in consistent with the previous published literature.

Kimeto, K'Aol and Njenga (2017) carried out a study aimed to establish the influence of inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation on organizational commitment in commercial banks in Kenya. The multiple regression results ($R^2=.722$, $p<.05$, $\beta = .249$, $p < .05$) indicated that inspirational motivation significantly predicted organizational commitment. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected. Further, the multiple regression results ($R^2=.734$, $p<.05$, $\beta = .366$, $p < .05$) indicated that Intellectual Stimulation significantly predicted organizational commitment. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected. Organizational culture showed a significant influence on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment as showed by the coefficients ($\beta = .229$, $p < .05$). The moderating variable organizational culture was also strongly correlated to organizational commitment, $r = .718$, $p < .05$ (Kimeto et al., 2017).

On other hand, Malik, Javed and Hassan (2017) carried out a study aimed to examine to investigate the impact of components pertains to transformational leadership (TL) by exercising dilemmas as employee (satisfaction & commitment), being engaged in Islamic banking sector; whereas TL components like; idealized influence (II), inspiration motivation (IM), intellectual stimulation (IS) and individualized consideration (IC) were taken into consideration. Findings of study reveal that idealized influence (II), inspiration motivation (IM), intellectual stimulation (IS) and individualized consideration (IC) have significant influence with respect to organizational commitment and job satisfaction of employees (Malik et al., 2017).

The relationship between Intellectual Stimulation and Organizational Commitment was statically positive and significant. In the quantitative data analysis, Intellectual Stimulation have 39.4% of predictive power (β) in achieving high level of Organizational Commitment (with p-value below the cut-off point 0.05), which means the Intellectual Stimulation affects the Organizational Commitment. Hence, H8 was supported. Speaking of the current study, Intellectual Stimulation is established to be significantly affecting the Organizational Commitment in Libya. Organizational Commitment among the employees' public banks in Libya is highly affected by the leaders' Behaviours that encourage creative and effortful problem solving, therefore, the Libyan public banks must encourage their leaders to build strong knowledge on being good couch for their subordinates. This result is in consistent with the previous published literature.

Moreover, the study of Kimeto, K'Aol and Njenga (2017) aimed to investigate the influence of inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation on organizational commitment in commercial banks in Kenya. The multiple regression results ($R^2=.722$, $p<.05$, $\beta = .249$, $p < .05$) indicated that inspirational motivation significantly predicted organizational commitment. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected. Further, the multiple regression results ($R^2=.734$, $p<.05$, $\beta = .366$, $p < .05$) indicated that Intellectual Stimulation significantly predicted organizational commitment. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected. Organizational culture showed a significant influence on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment as showed by the coefficients ($\beta = .229$, $p < .05$). The moderating variable organizational culture was also strongly correlated to organizational commitment, $r = .718$, $p < .05$ (Kimeto et al., 2017).

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In addition, the objective of the research conducted by Al-Quraan (2016) was to explore the impact of transformational leadership (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) on organizational commitment (affective, normative and continuance) at Jordan Ahli Bank from branches' employee's view. The present study has shown that transformational leadership dimensions (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) have significant impact on organizational commitment (affective, normative and continuance) at Jordan Ahli Bank (Al-Quraan, 2016).

The relationship between Individualized consideration and Organizational Commitment was statically positive, however, it was statically insignificant. In the quantitative data analysis, Individualized consideration was found to have only 3.7% of predictive power (β) in achieving a high level of Organizational Commitment (with p-value above the cut-off point 0.05), which means the Individualized consideration have small and insignificant effect on the Organizational Commitment. Hence, H9 was rejected. Speaking of the current study, Individualized consideration is established to be insignificantly affecting the Organizational Commitment in Libya. When a leader is having empathy on the subordinates, and more importantly provides support for the individual development needs of followers, such acts can ensure the Organizational Commitment in Libyan public banks. This result is in consistent with the previous published literature.

The study of Malik, Javed and Hassan (2017) aimed to investigate the impact of components pertains to transformational leadership (TL) by exercising dilemmas as employee (satisfaction & commitment), being engaged in Islamic banking sector; whereas TL components like; idealized influence (II), inspiration motivation (IM), intellectual stimulation (IS) and individualized consideration (IC) were taken into consideration. Findings of study reveal that idealized influence (II), inspiration motivation (IM), intellectual stimulation (IS) and individualized consideration (IC) have significant influence with respect to organizational commitment and job satisfaction of employees (Malik et al., 2017).

In addition, the study of Al-Quraan (2016) aimed at identifying the impact of transformational leadership (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) on organizational commitment (affective, normative and continuance) at Jordan Ahli Bank from branches' employee's view. The present study has

shown that transformational leadership dimensions (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) have significant impact on organizational commitment (affective, normative and continuance) at Jordan Ahli Bank (Al-Quraan, 2016).

7. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

In practice, this study has a number of practical implications for the Leadership of the Banking sector. The study suggests that with proper idealized influence from the leaders, the employee performance will be higher, therefore, putting this into consideration when training the leaders inside the Libyan public banks. Like what has been found previously by other researchers, the leaders' inspirational motivation is an essential element in employee performance, it means that with more meaningful messages conveyed between a leader and a subordinate, the employee performance will be better. Moreover, intellectual stimulation of the leaders of the Libyan public banks is important, but it was proved as insignificant toward employee performance. However, Leaders in the Libyan public banks are lacking such a trait which is affecting the employee performance. Finally, Individualized consideration is also an important element when talking about the level of employee performance.

The purpose of this study is to determine what factors are related to the Employees performance. The study included Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individualized consideration as independent variables. In order to achieve better results from this study, the researcher has introduced Organizational Commitment as a mediating effect on the relationship between the variables. The target population for this study are employees working for Public Sector banks in Libya. This study suggests significant relationship between Idealized Influences, Inspirational Motivation, and Organizational Commitment from hand, and employee performance in the Libyan public banks from another hand, which support what was found in the majority of the previous published literature. But unlike the majority of the published literature, Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized consideration was found to be insignificant with employee performance in the Libyan public banks.

8. FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has a lot of potentials, many of them could be addressed here in order to make sure that future researchers are aware of them. Whereas, focusing on other banks (other than public banks) in Libya, like private banks as case study with systematic selection would generate different types of results on the factors that affect Employee performance in the Libyan public banks. Moreover, studying a larger sample size may return with more options in the analysis and results. In addition, following the mix methods (i.e., including the interviewing) as a methodology for future studies would spot the light on the employee performance and opinions that are worthy of studying.

Furthermore, in this study, Organizational commitment was considered as mediating variable while a good sum of studies considered studying the Organizational commitment dimensions as independent variables for the employee performance, it is recommended that the future studies may consider the Organizational commitment dimensions as part of holistic study and associate it with the employee performance. In the end, the researcher recommends redoing the same study but with other independent variables would come back with different determinants of the employee performance in the Libyan public banks. Since this study considered only public banks operating in Tripoli, the researcher recommends redoing the same study on different types of banks, especially private banks inside and outside Tripoli in the future.

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